

AUTOMATIC FAULT DETECTION AND DIAGNOSIS IN PHOTOVOLTAIC PLANTS BASED ON CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT: This work aims to discover efficient and reliable machine-learning architectures and models for highly automated fault detection, diagnosis and predictive maintenance using the real-time flow of operational data generated at utility-scale photovoltaic plants. Our models consists of Convolutional Neural Networks which are trained on datasets which have been assembled from several years of operational data from about a dozen PV plants located in Europe and Latin America, with an approximate overall generation power of 1 GW, and different types of modules, tracking and terrain. We do minimal data preprocessing to construct our models. We use both 1-D and 2-D convolutional neural networks. For 2-D convolutional neural networks, we transform the time series into images by using Markov Field Transform, Recurrence plots, and Gramian Angular Fields. The performance of our models so far does not show significant improvements over other systems published in the literature, but it must be taken into consideration that the use of real operational data entails a significant challenge, when compared to simulated environments and small plant scenarios. We are improving the architectures and algorithms for higher reliability, a wider catalog of scenarios, and concurrent faults. We are also working on knowledge transfer among PV plants.

Keywords: Photovoltaic systems, Fault detection, Machine learning

1 INTRODUCTION

Sustained and significant growth of large photovoltaic (PV) plant portfolios demands smart automation of many operational aspects to achieve efficient plant operation. Fault detection and diagnosis are areas which can greatly benefit from advanced automated monitoring.

Utility-scale PV plants are extensively sensorised and produce large amounts of detailed operational data. Nowadays these data are used to detect faults using relatively rigid and simple methods, such as threshold crossing, statistical analysis, comparison between measured and simulated yields, and various heuristics. However, the unsophisticated nature of these methods means that many subtle faults go unnoticed, and that it is not uncommon to generate operational alarms which are unreliable or misdirected. Preventive maintenance, that is, early detection and diagnosis of conditions which do not currently impact operation but may do so in the short or mid-term, is even more of a *rara avis*.

Many AI techniques have recently been proposed for PV plant fault detection and diagnosis, but they tend to concentrate in specific problem cases, and in most cases have been evaluated with small and synthetic datasets. [1] shows a review of several previous work that use machine learning (ML) techniques for photovoltaic fault detection. [2] and [3] show the use of deep learning (DL) models based on artificial neural networks (ANN) combined with a digital twin (DT) to detect and diagnose faults in a simulated environment.

Such previous works show that applying ML and DL techniques can improve fault detection and diagnosis processes, by using images of PV modules and/or PV plant sensorisation data as their inputs. But they have mostly been tested in simulated scenarios, where many sources of environmental noise which are present in real PV plants are not taken into account, such as different electrical characteristics of the devices, aging, weather conditions, sensing variability and inaccuracies, concurrence of multiple faults, etc.

Our work aims to apply ML and DL techniques inspired by those which have shown their potential in simulated or small scale environments to real utility-scale

PV plant sensorisation data. We intend to discover efficient and reliable machine learning architectures and models for the purpose of highly automated fault detection, diagnosis, and predictive maintenance, inspecting in real-time the data flow generated by sensors available at utility-scale PV plants. This will allow to optimize the operation of utility-scale PV plants, and to create the foundations for a reference description of data flow, fault classification and fault diagnosis.

2 DATASET DESCRIPTION

We have assembled a dataset of real utility-scale PV plant operational data, which covers several years of operation in about a dozen PV plants located in Europe and Latin America, with an approximate overall generation power of 1 GW. These PV plants also have different characteristics (monofacial vs bifacial, single-axis tracking vs fixed, flat vs uneven terrain...). The dataset includes detailed electrical sensorisation, as well as weather and irradiance data, with a time resolution in the order of 5-15 minutes.

These PV plants have suffered different faults and anomalies over the years, and we have carefully reviewed the data to construct a high-quality labelled dataset which can be used for AI model creation and performance evaluation. Over 30 types of faults and anomalies have been identified, although some of the cases are so rare that they are hardly useful for model training.

Among the different scenarios that we are addressing, in this paper we present three illustrative cases (the first two for fault detection, and the last one for predictive maintenance). They are:

Tracker target error: when the actual tracker position (continuous blue line) differs from the optimal objective position (dotted orange line), as shown on Figure 1.

Figure 1. Example of tracker target error

Open string: when a string is disconnected, and its production is therefore lost. Causes could be open fuses, burned out connectors, manual operations, etc. Figure 2 shows yield differences between two stringboxes, where the one corresponding to the continuous blue line has an open string.

Figure 2. Example of open string

Anomalous element temperature: when temperature monitoring shows a pattern that does not comply with the correct operation of an element, such as an inverter or a transformer. This anomaly does not initially affect operation, but early identification and preventive maintenance will prevent future major problems. Figure 3 shows anomalous temperature in the inverter plotted with a continuous blue line.

Figure 3. Example of anomalous inverter temperature

3 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

We are using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to create fault detection and diagnosis models, trained and validated with the datasets described in the previous section. CNNs are frequently used for image processing applications, while sensor data are typically time series of real values. We are using both 1-D and 2-D CNNs.

Convolutional neural networks have been frequently employed for image processing applications, where they have excelled at pattern recognition and classification, even in the presence of various types of noise. Most sensor data from PV plants are time series of real values, but some techniques, such as those described in [2] and [3], can be used to convert them into 2D matrices, which provide a visual representation suitable for effective analysis with a CNN. This will also allow us to confirm whether this approach is as effective with real operational data as with synthetic simulated data.

We are avoiding elaborate raw data preprocessing, as we intend to build models that can be efficiently applied and transferred among PV plants without the need of significant customization. So far, we are using simple preprocessing steps, such as cleaning unavailable sensorisation, normalizing measurements, grouping time series of similar devices, and selecting significant variables.

For 1-D CNNs, we are using mono and multi-variate time series which have been preprocessed as described above.

For 2-D CNNs, we are transforming mono and multi-variate time series data into 2-D images with several preprocessing techniques: Markov Transition Field, Recurrence Plots, and Gramian Angular Field. These techniques preserve temporal structure information and can be effectively processed by 2-D CNNs.

A Markov Transition Field transform (MTF) first discretizes continuous values in a times series using quantization techniques. Subsequently a Markov transition matrix is computed, where each element represents the probability of transitioning between two discrete states. That matrix is used to construct an image where each pixel corresponds to the transition probability between two states over time.

A Recurrence Plot is a 2-D matrix representation of time series in dynamic systems where each point (i,j) represents whether the system's state at time i is similar to the state at time j , that is, the phase space trajectory visits roughly the same area at both times.

A Gramian Angular Field transform (GAN) first maps the time series data into polar coordinates and then builds a corresponding Gram matrix. Essentially, each time point is mapped to a vector in polar coordinates where the temporal index is treated as the radius and the normalized magnitude as the inverse angle. The Gram matrix is a 2-D matrix where point (i,j) is computed from the inner product of vectors at times i and j .

4 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

We have trained a validated several 1-D and 2-D CNN architectures with the datasets described in previous sections. The architecture hyperparameter sets have been optimized with KerasTuner [4]. Figure 4 shows the f1-score achieved by our CNNs for the three example fault and anomaly scenarios described in a previous section.

Figure 4. *f1-score by algorithm and fault*

These results so far do not show significant improvements over other systems published in the literature. However, it must be taken into consideration that our approach is working on real data from utility-scale PV plants, which is proving to be harder because real data typically contains more noise than those generated by simulation, and the amount of training examples is much more limited.

This work is ongoing and our next steps are:

- Use other improved DL architectures and ML algorithms. For instance, we are planning to experiment with ConvMixer architectures and pre-trained image classification models.
- Apply our models to a wider catalog of faults and anomalies, in particular to concurrent faults.
- Use synthetically generated samples to train our models where real data is scarce, and determine its usability to real conditions.
- Study the feasibility and procedure of transferring knowledge and models obtained from some PV plants to new PV plants, with as little customization as possible.

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